

Elements Of Economic And Educational Capital Of Youth In Cieszyn Silesia (Polish-Czech borderland)

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Abstract

In class societies, school certificates are not adequate indicators of educational capital. However, in post-communist and transition societies the relations between capitals look differently. It appears that in Poland today, the quality of life is primarily determined by a specific style of consumption and a specific standard of possession, and to a lesser extent by cultural competence resulting from the position held. This article analyses the economic situation of the respondents and its impact on decisions concerning the choice of tertiary education.

Introduction

In class societies, school certificates are not adequate indicators of educational capital (Bourdieu, 1984, 13). However, in a post-communist and transition societies, the relations between capitals look differently. Ziółkowski (2012, 20) notes that in Poland today, the quality of life is primarily determined by a specific style of consumption and a specific standard of possession, and to a lesser extent by cultural competence resulting from the position held. This article provides an analysis of the economic situation of the respondents and its impact on decisions concerning the respondents' choice of tertiary education. The article discusses a hypothesis about the relationship between the financial situation and the preferences in the choice of tertiary education.

Research Methodology

Research Sample

The total number of students of the region's secondary schools in 2012/2013 school year was 5413. The sample size was calculated based on the formula: $n = N / ((1 + d^2(N-1)) / u_a^2 pq)$ (Greń, 1984, 246). The final sample, after about 20 questionnaires were excluded due to the missing data, numbered 318 respondents, and the error (d) reached 5.3%, which is a fully satisfactory result. The survey was carried out between October 2012 and January 2013. The respondents were students from upper-secondary schools (with and without A-level). The year of birth of the vast majority (98.3%) of the students, was between 1994 and 1997. The research was carried out in Southern Poland, in Cieszyn Silesia, in schools located in Cieszyn, Skoczów, Ustroń and Istebna.

Instruments and Procedures

Data was collected using a single questionnaire filled by students during their classes. The questionnaire included 71 questions and was divided into 4 sections. The first section referred to socio-economic and demographic data, the second section to cultural capital, the third section to social capital, and the fourth to educational capital. This paper presents only the findings concerning the educational capital.

Research Results

Material and living conditions of the respondents

In the study of cultural and social capital, the material and living conditions of respondents are particularly important. (Kłopot, Kozdraś, Trojanowski 2012: 51). To examine the standard of living, I used basic determinants, such as professional activity and education of parents, and the subjective appraisal of one's economic situation. I did not include the question on income because the situation in which the survey was

conducted, i.e. during classes at school, despite ensuring absolute attention, did not guarantee full privacy. According to the survey data (table 1), 7% indicated their parents were unemployed, and combined with those whose parents were without a permanent source of income (full-time job), for example casual employment, the proportion of those whose parents were in precarious occupational situation reached 12.5%. This data more or less coincides with the Cieszyn region's unemployment rate in 2010, which was 10.0%. At the same time, overall Poland's unemployment rate in 2010 was ca. 11%. The data on the source of income, not based on full-time employment, is particularly interesting. It turns out that in the case of almost 28% of respondents, their parents support their households thanks to their own initiative, which means that they either operate their own business or work in a liberal profession. This is a large figure which indicates that almost one-third of all parents are active on the labour market. It can be assumed that this is an important factor having impact on the behaviour of children who, following their parents' example, are more willing to undertake their own activities in various fields. Twice as many men as women ran a business, but women were better educated. It should be noted that the majority of household budgets were based on income provided by both parents. This is confirmed by the data informing about the preferred family model.

Table 1. Parents' occupational activity

type of activity	N=296 father	N=301 mother
Full-time job	49.3 %	55.5 %
Own business	17.2 %	8.0 %
Liberal profession	17.2 %	13.3 %
Retirement (pension)	8.1 %	6.0 %
Casual employment (e.g., odd job)	5.1 %	5.6 %
Unemployed	2.7 %	11.3 %
In education	0.3 %	0.3 %
Total	100 %	100 %

Table 2. Type of family

Which way of family life best describes your family?	N=281
Father and mother devote more or less the same amount of time to work, they both share equal amount of time to take care of the home and children.	63.8 %
Only father works to meet the needs of the family, and mother takes care of housekeeping and child-rearing.	20.1 %
Only mother works to meet the needs of the family, and father takes care of the housekeeping and child-rearing.	4.4 %

In the context of resources related to educational capital, one must note an impact of the way the family functions on internalisation of basic values (table 2). Almost two-thirds of respondents indicated that in their households a partnership-based division of family responsibilities prevails. About 20% of respondents described their family model as traditional, while only slightly more than 4% are in households where mother is the head of the family. The data indicate that the community of Cieszyn Silesia as a whole prefers traditional values, including a division of the traditional role of father and mother, internalised through Protestant or Catholic upbringing, in which there is.

Table 3. Parent's education level

Education	Father N=297	Mother N=302
Basic vocational lower secondary without A-level	44.8 %	27.8 %
Upper secondary with A-level	33.0 %	41.4 %

Tertiary (including professional and academic degrees)	17.1 %	26.5 %
Primary education	5.1 %	4.3 %
Total	100 %	100 %

The respondents' answers show more mothers than fathers having completed upper-secondary or tertiary education (table 3). This is also confirmed by the comparison of the average value of the education rank of women and men, which was 4.06 rank points for mothers and 3.74 rank points for fathers. On the other hand, vocational education prevails among men, which translates into service activities for which the region of Cieszyn Silesia is famous.

Table 4. Economic situation

Which of the following statements best describes your household situation?	N=303
We live modestly, we have to be very economical on a daily basis.	4.6 %
We live averagely, it is enough for our basic needs, but we have to save for more serious purchases.	39.6 %
We live well , it is enough for us even without special savings.	48.2 %
We live very well, we can afford luxury.	7.6 %
Total	100 %

The respondents were asked to assess their households' economic situation subjectively (table 4). Only a minority (just above 12%) indicated extreme responses, i.e. felt they lived modestly or very well. The rest indicated average or good economic situation. As in the case of professional activity, the data may suggest the existence of a middle class due to a large proportion of households where parents were self-employed or in liberal professions. The vast majority (87.8%) assess their economic conditions as average and good.

Relations between economic and educational capital

According to Bourdieu, cultural competence is one of the necessary but insufficient factors that enable one to enjoy the form of art. Another factor is the material situation (Bourdieu, 1996: 60-70). He sees the relationship between the type of preferred art (in this case formal, abstract art) and the attitude towards the world. Individuals who do not have to worry about the economic situation do not take art literally.

Aesthetic distancing, understood as the ability to abstract from practical goals, according to the French sociologist, develops thanks to experiencing the world in a way detached from necessity, i.e., when it is possible to participate in activities that have no practical purpose, such as school exercises or contemplation of works of art. This ability is manifested, among others, by keeping distance to the world. This ability, according to the French sociologist, is closely related to the position in the social space. It is this skill that makes us move away from taking art literally. The taste that individuals present, results from the aesthetic distancing they have or do not have, therefore its subsequent classification will be mutually exclusive. (Bourdieu, 1984, 56-58).

Polish (national) and Cieszyn Silesia (regional) Perspectives

However, it seems that this relation does not fully correspond to the Polish reality. This lifestyle of an individual, in which we can observe either admiration for impractical things or, on the contrary, their incomprehension and reluctance towards them, as Bourdieu puts it, manifests itself completely differently in Polish society. Ziolkowski notes that in contemporary Poland the quality of life is primarily determined by a specific style of consumption and a specific standard of possession, and to a lesser extent by cultural competence resulting from the position held (Bourdieu, 1985, 57). Thus, material objects play a special role in manifesting the individual's position. In the eyes of a significant part of society, the most important stratification criterion is access to material values. Purchasing possibilities are to be confirmed by a high level of conspicuous consumption, and the sense of doing so is that they are noticed and assessed in one's social circle (Ziolkowski, 2012, 20).

Therefore, according to the Polish sociologist, a significant part of the society expects usefulness from material values, an example of which is the growing interest of young people in 'practical' education, which is expected to ensure good earnings. And the motivation to take them up is driven by practical calculations rather than personal interests or job-related hobbies. In this context, it is worth examining how this situation manifests itself

among young people from the Polish-Czech borderland region. First of all, the vast majority of the respondents (84.5%) intends to continue their education. As far as the approach to post-secondary education is concerned, just more than one-half of the respondents consider their own interests and job-related hobbies as crucial in choosing their studies, and thus seem to ignore the practical and economic aspects (table 5). Slightly fewer respondents (45.9%) are motivated by utilitarian values. Another question (table 6) shows that young people's education is, in their own view, important for their families, as over 72.7% of the respondents declared such interest on the part of their parents. 26.3% of young people stated that their parents believe that children should decide about themselves and their education. However, when choosing the school itself, practical aspects turned out to be the most important, i.e. accessibility and location (59.1%). An interest in academic profile of a class was indicated by 25.2% (table 7). One can also observe the relationship between the material situation and the choice of studies. The better the financial situation, the more frequently 'impractical' fields of study were preferred (table 8).

Table 5. Preferences in the choice of fields of study

Motivations	N=246	Frequency
1. Personal interest	50.4 %	124
2. Practical concerns	45.9 %	113
3. Mixed model	3.7 %	9

Table 6. Parents' involvement in respondents' school matters

Are your parents involved in your education?	N=315	Frequency
They are interested in my education	72.4 %	228
They believe I should decide for myself	26.3 %	83
Mixed model	1.3 %	4
Total	100 %	315

Table 7. What plays the greatest role in choosing a school?

Factors	N=318
Accessibility and location	59.1 %
Class academic profile	25.2 %
Friend's influence	7.5 %
Parents' will	6.0 %
Future	1.3 %

Table 8. Influence of the financial situation on the choice of studies.

Which of the following statements best describes your household situation?	Preferences in the choice of fields of study		
	Personal interest	Practical concerns	Mixed model
We live averagely, we have to be very economical on a daily basis.	9.2%	65.8%	32%
We live on average, it is enough for our basic needs, but we have to save for more serious purchases.	16.4%	17.6	26.7%
We live well , it is enough for us even without special savings.	38.3%	7.9%	19.9%
We live very well, we can afford luxury.	36.1%	8.7%	21.4%
Total	100%	100%	100%

Conclusions

Young people from the Cieszyn Silesia have great opportunities to develop their interests and to devote their time to study, because their families' relatively large economic capital. More than one-third of parents show their own initiative in the labour market. This means that a large group of Cieszyn residents are independent of the state and of large corporations as far as looking for a job is concerned. The hypothesis about the relationship between the financial situation and preferences in the choice of tertiary education was confirmed.

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